

CHEMICAL SCIENCES

CHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF MINERAL WATERS OF THE SOUTHERN REGION

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ABSTRACT

In the research work, water samples were taken from mineral and thermal springs of Lerik-Masalli region and their chemical composition was determined. The geographical coordinates of the location of the water samples were determined, cation content and pH values were studied. As a result, 23 out of 34 cations were less than 0,1% in water. The maximum amount of Sr^{2+} cation was determined in TM- 88 in same waters. The water in this article ranges from PH-7.28 to 8.36. In general, it was found that the PH of the given waters was weakly alkaline. Only Pig Swallowing Spring show an almost neutral environment (PH= 7.28). This is due to the fact that the temperature of this spring is higher than the others (64°C). Usually, because the PH value of thermal waters haws a weak acid property, they are used for treatment and drinking.

Keywords: Cation, thermal, mineral waters, pH, inductive-related, Donuz uten, Buludul.

Introduction.

Mineral waters are one of the most important minerals in the territory of the Republic of Azerbaijan. They are different in chemical composition, they are used in drinking water supply in the farm, for treatment purposes and in industry. High-temperature (60-1150C) waters with a large thermal energy source were also discovered in the Republic through deep exploration (2000-3000m) wells [1-4]. The complexity of the natural conditions of the republic has influenced the different types of waters in the area, their formation and distribution: Mesozoic-Modern age sedimentary rocks with different lithological composition in Düzen regions have a huge reserve of agricultural, drinking, ground and artesian waters [5-7]

Groundwater is found almost everywhere in modern sediments. [3-4] As a result of active water exchange in the foothills, these waters are located somewhat deeper. Their mineralization is 1g/l; its chemical composition is calcium-hydrocarbonate. The mineralization of these waters is approximately 1g/l, the chemical composition is calcium-hydrocarbonate, and they are used in the water supply of cities and villages and in the irrigation of fields. [8-10]

Purpose of the study

Water samples were taken from mineral and thermal springs and their chemical composition was determined.

Experimental part.

In the course of the study, a number of titration and atomic adsorption methods from different photocalorimeters were used. [2-5-6] Different types of reagents were used for the determination of each component.

This article presents a complete chemical analysis of thermal and mineral water sources of various functions located in the Southern region of the Republic of

Azerbaijan as part of complex research in the field of physical properties measurement.

The thermal waters of Donuz uten-Masalli district rise to the surface of the earth at an altitude of 500-550 meters above sea level. On the right bank of Vilash river, 500m west of the water source of Erkivan village, Masalli region, there is a spring of pig-sucking [photo 1-2] at a distance of 30m from each other. It is a thermal water source with a temperature of 65-90oC, which once had 20 exits and a debit of 1.6 million liters/day, and currently has 3 known exits. This natural resource is currently not properly used. Although the water of this terminal spring is not safe to drink, it has great therapeutic value by taking baths.

The composition of the waters of this spring differs from other mineral waters, and the elements in the water affect the skin in different ways. For sensitive skin, water with a low salt content is suitable (in this case, excessively salty water will only cause irritation).

Calcium and magnesium in thermal water strengthen blood vessels and soothe skin irritation, silicon slows down aging, zinc protects skin from free radicals, and iron improves skin. These elements improve the functioning of the skin's protective mechanisms so that it better resists negative environmental factors (air pollution, low temperature, etc.).

Bülüdül spring is known for its springs located in Bülüdül village of Lerik region. Bülüdül spring of the same name [1-3] of the village is a source of surprise not only for local residents, but also for guests who come here. Surrounded by steep cliffs, the source of the spring remains a mystery to this day.

According to the villagers, 16 years ago the spring had one eye. After the earthquake in the area in 1998, water springs appeared in the other part of the rock.

Figure 1.

Figure 2.

Bulüdül spring is known for its springs located in Bülüdül village of Lerik region. Bülüdül spring of the same name [1-3] of the village is a source of surprise not only for local residents, but also for guests who come here. Surrounded by steep cliffs, the source of the spring remains a mystery to this day.

According to the villagers, 16 years ago the spring had one eye. After the earthquake in the area in 1998, water springs appeared in the other part of the rock.

In this article, the cation content of water samples taken from Masalli, Lerik regions was analyzed with high precision. Cation analyzes were performed on a TRIS Interpit, Optical Emission Spectrometer atomic emission spectrometer (cation) with inductively coupled plasma.

Results and discussion

The water of the spring, which has a total of 26 types of chemical elements, is also healing. The water of the spring plays an indispensable role in the treatment of a number of diseases in the human body. People suffering from kidney, joint, back, leg pain, fungal disease on the feet have regained their health by using this medicinal water.

The water of Buludul spring is also used as table water. During the day, thousands of plastic containers are filled and taken to the territory of the village and neighboring villages.

In general, there are about 1000 springs in Lerik region.

Figure 3. Buludul spring

Figure 4. Buludul village

Figure 5. Buludul spring

Figure 6. Buludul village

Figure 7. Hamarmesha spring Picture

Figure 8. Aliabad spring

As can be seen from the table, the PH-I of the water samples varies from 7.28 to 8.36. In general, the taken waters were found to be PH-I, weakly alkaline. Only Pig Swallowing Spring shows an almost neutral environment (PH=7.28). This is due to the fact that the temperature of this spring is higher than the others (640C). As the pH value of thermal waters is usually weakly acidic, they are usually used for therapeutic purposes and not for drinking.

Conclusions:

1. The results of analysis of 34 cations in water during the analysis are shown in the diagram. As can be seen, cations such as Na^+ , Ca^{2+} , K^+ , Mg^{2+} , S^{4+} and Sr^{2+} are the main components in each of the water samples. The TM-88 water sample has a higher degree of minerality than the others. The amount of Na^+ ion in TM-88 is more. This indicates that there is a lot of NaCl - salt in the water, the amount of Sr^{2+} cation is maximally high in the TM-88 water sample (100 ml/l), despite the fact that it is very small in other waters. This is due to

the high temperature of thermal waters. The main advantage is Na^+ , Ca^{2+} , K^+ , Mg^{2+} , S^{4+} , Sr^{2+} , relatively few B^{3+} , Ba^{2+} , Li^+ , Si^{2+} , these cations.

2. In TM-90 (Haftoni spring Hovil village) [Figure 5], Mg^{2+} ions reach 40 mg/l. Mg in these waters can be considered more appropriate for drinking purposes.

3. According to the results of the cation analysis, 23 cations below 0.1% were detected. It can be said that heavy metal ions are not found in these waters.

These are Cu, Fe, Rb, Cd, Zn, Ti, etc. Since these heavy metal ions are dangerous, if they are found in water, it is important to remove them by adsorption method. In this regard, since radioactive, heavy metal ions were not detected in the water we took, we continued our research with the analysis of other mineral springs of the southern region.

Currently, water samples taken from 5 points in the Southern region have been accurately analyzed.

Table 1.

Geographical coordinates of the location of the analyzed thermal and mineral samples of the southern region

№	Name of the place where the water sample was taken	Conventional name	En circle	Length
1	Masallı - Pig swallower	TM-88		
2	Lerik- Buludul	TM-89		
3	Lerik - Haftoni spring (Hovil village)	TM-90		
4	Lerik - Smooth forest	TM-91		
5	Lerik- Aliabad (Veri village)	TM-92		

Table 2.

Values of pH of water samples

№	Name of the place where the water sample was taken	Conventional name	pH
1	Masallı - Pig swallower	TM-88	7.28
2	Lerik- Buludul	TM-89	8.36
3	Lerik - Haftoni spring (Hovil village)	TM-90	8.12
4	Lerik - Smooth forest	TM-91	8.22
5	Lerik- Aliabad (Veri village)	TM-92	8.36

As can be seen from the table, the PH-I of the water samples varies from 7.28 to 8.36. In general, the taken waters were found to be PH-I [Figure 9-10], weakly alkaline. Only Pig Swallowing Spring shows an almost neutral environment (PH=7.28). This is due to the fact that the temperature of this spring is higher than the others (640C). As the pH value of thermal waters is usually weakly acidic, they are usually used for therapeutic purposes and not for drinking.

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